

COST-EFFECTIVENESS IN PROTECTING WEEDS THAT CAUSE SERIOUS DAMAGE IN IRRIGATED GRAIN AREAS USING HERBICIDES

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Abstract: On this day, reducing spending on the development of agricultural products is a prerequisite for indicating the profitability of agricultural products. This can be achieved by increasing crop yields. Carrying out chemical treatments based on weather conditions in timely places is one of the most important factors in increasing productivity.

Key words: Grain, harvest, option, gumimax and herbicide, weed, fight, spending, net income, profitability, efficiency.

Аннотация: Бугунки кунда қишлоқ хўжалик маҳсулотларини ишлаб чиқишда сарф-ҳаражатларни камайтириш қишлоқ хўжалиги маҳсулот рентабиллигини кўрсатадиган асосий шарти ҳисобланади. Бунда экинларнинг ҳосилдорлигини ошириш йўли билан эришиш мумкин. Ўз вақтида жойларда об-ҳаво шароитдан келиб чиққан ҳолда кимёвий ишловларини ўтказиш ҳосилдорликни оширишнинг энг муҳим омиллардан бири ҳисобланади.

Калит сўзлар: Дон, ҳосил, вариант, гумимакс ва гербицид, бегона ўтлар, қарши кураш, сарф-ҳаражат, соф даромад, рентабиллик, самарадорлик.

Аннотация: В этот день сокращение расходов на разработку сельскохозяйственной продукции является обязательным условием для указания рентабельности сельскохозяйственной продукции. Этого можно достичь за счет повышения урожайности сельскохозяйственных культур. Своевременное проведение химических обработок в зависимости от погодных условий является одним из наиболее важных факторов повышения производительности

Ключевые слова: Зерно, урожай, вариант, гумимакс и гербицид, сорняки, борьба, расходы, чистый доход, рентабельность, эффективность.

It should be noted that in our country, weeds cause the growth and development of the wheat plant, decrease the grain quality, and cause the loss of 30-40% of the crop [5]. Therefore, it is necessary to treat weeds with chemical herbicides and eliminate them.

Under the leadership of the head of our country, rapid reforms are being implemented in the agricultural sector to increase grain yield. Reform of the

agrarian sector is defined in the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan and the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture until 2030. As the head of our country Sh.Mirziyoev pointed out, it is not for nothing that the factor that gives the fastest results in reducing poverty and increasing the income of the rural population is the sharp increase in productivity and efficiency in agriculture [3].

In weed-infested fields, as the growth and development of the grain lags behind, it is natural that both yield and quality indicators decrease. In our fields, farmers use 2 mls of herbicide per season to control weeds in grain fields and even more in heavy weed fields.

The effective use of herbicides in the control of weeds growing between crops allows significant savings in the cost of their elimination, and the possibility of new herbicides. Timely weeding of the fields ensures a higher grain yield and higher economic efficiency.

Taking these circumstances into account, we conducted research on increasing wheat productivity in 2019-2021. In our study, we took into account the economic efficiency of controlling the main weeds in wheat.

To find the economic efficiency of winter wheat cultivation, the total income was found by multiplying the yield obtained from the experimental options by the state purchase price. Profitability is determined by dividing net income by expenses. From the results of the conducted research, it should be noted that grain cultivation is an economically profitable crop and is of great importance in improving the financial and economic activity of farmers and farms.

In order to determine the economic effectiveness of the results of our research, we took into account the total costs for growing grain on 1 hectare: the costs for the combined use of Gumimax and herbicides and for their separate use.

In addition, the cost of 1 quintal of grain, gross income, net income, increase in net income and profitability levels were determined.

Economic efficiency was calculated when using herbicides. In the Entopic (standard) option, where herbicide was used in the usual way, the total costs were 6217607.2 soums/ha. XimAskil 10% ke. herbicide 6337607.2 soums/ha in the variant used at 0.3 l/ha, Demetra em.k herbicide 6457607.2 soums/ha in the variant used at the rate of 0.5 l/ha, Katsumii 24 es in the variant used at the rate 0.3 l/ha 6417607 2 soums/ha, Khimstar 75% v.d.g 20 g/ha is used for 5967607.2 soums/ha, Adyu 0.2+Bomba v.d.g 30 g/ha is used for 6527607.2 soums/ha was a cost.

If 5,807,607.23 soums were spent on 1 hectare from the beginning of the season, the expenses for the use of herbicides were calculated as follows.

1). Entopic e.c. 1.0 liter - 360,000 soums; 2). XimAskial 10% 1.0 liter - 480000; 3). Demeter em.k. 1.0 liter - 600,000 soums; 4). Katsumi et al. 1.0 liter - 560,000 soums; 5). Khimstar 75% vdg. 20gr/ha - 110,000 soums; 6). Adyu+Bomba etc. 1.0 liter - 670,000 soums; 7). Gumimax 1 g/ha 500 g/mm - 60,000 soums; Application of herbicides for 1 hectare - 50,000 soums;

The cost of 1 kg/g of wheatgrass in the conventional method was 236.1 soums in the control option, 496.2 soums/ha in the Etalon option, 466.6 soums/ha in the XimAskial 10% option, 536.2 soums/ha in the Demetra KE option, Katsumii 24 was 559.6 soums in the ES option, 478.6 soums/ha in the Khimstar 75% V.D.G option, and 595.7 soums/ha in the Adyu+Bomba V.D.G option (Table 1).

In our study, the gross income from the sale of the harvest obtained from 1 hectare was calculated as 6851000 soums/ha in the control option, 9145000 soums/ha in the Entopic (standard) option, 9067500 soums/ha in the XimAskial 10% option, 9873500 soums/ha in the Demetra em.k option, Katsumii 24 es option 10044000 soums/ha, Khimstar 75 v.d.g option 8633500 soums/ha, Adyu+Bombav.d.g option 10602000 soums/ha. Katsumii 24 es option 3193000 soums/ha, Adyu+Bomba v.d.g option 3751000 soums more gross income was obtained compared to the control and benchmark option (Table 1).

The net income from the sale of grain is 1043392.8 soums/ha in the control option, this indicator is higher in the options with herbicides, 2927392.8 soums/ha in the Etalon option, 2729892.8 soums/ha in the XimAskial 10% option, 3415892 in the Demetra em.k option, 8 soums/ha, Katsumii 24es option 3626392.8 soums/ha, Khimstar 75 v.d.g option 2665892.8 soums/ha, Adyu+Bomba v.d.g option 4074392.8 soums/ha, compared to control 3031000 soums It was observed that it is 1,147,000 soums/ha higher than the benchmark option.

It was observed that in the Demetra em.k variant, compared to the control, the net income was 2372500 soums/ha, Katsumii 24 es variant was 2583000 soums/ha.

The rate of profitability was equal to 18.0% in the control option, in the remaining options, this indicator was 25 - 38.5% higher than the control option, in the option where Demetra em.k was used at the rate of 0.5 l/ha, it was 52.9%, this indicator is 56.5% in the case of Katsumii 24 es 0.3 l/ha, Adyu+Bomba v.d.g 0.2 l/ha; and in the variant used at the rate of 30 g/ha, it was 62.4%.

When using herbicides together with Gumimax , the costs incurred in the Ento PIK(Etalon) 10% + Gumimax option were 6277607.2 soums, while the new herbicides used together with Gumimax , Khim Askial 10% KE + Gumimax, cost 6397607.2 soums, while Demetra em. K herbicide 6517607.2 soums/ha in the version used at the rate of 0.5 l/ha, Katsumii 24 es 6477607.2 soums/ha in the version used at the rate of 0.3 l/ha, Khimstar 75% v.d.g 20 g/ha in option 6027607.2 soums/ha, Adyu+Bomba v.d.g 0.2 l/ha; 6587607.2 soums/ha were spent at the rate of 30 g/ha (Table 1).

Table 1

Economic efficiency of application of new herbicides in grain fields

No	variety	Options	Productivity	Cost	Price of 1 kg of grain, soum	Gross income , thousand soums	Net income , thousand soums	The cost of 1 kg of grain, soum	Rate of return, %
Regular use of herbicides (Average 2019-2021)									
1	Shams	Control	44,2	5807607	1550	6851000	1043393	236,1	18
2		Ento PIK (Etalon) 10%	59	6217607	1550	9145000	2927393	496,2	47,1
3		Khim Askial 10% KE	58,5	6337607	1550	9067500	2729893	466,6	43,1
4		Demetra em. K	63,7	6457607	1550	9873500	3415893	536,2	52,9
5		Katsumii 24 ES	64,8	6417607	1550	10044000	3626393	559,6	56,5
6		Khimstar 75% V.D.G	55,7	5967607	1550	8633500	2665893	478,6	44,7
7		Adyu+Bomba V.D.G	68,4	6527607	1550	10602000	4074393	595,7	62,4
Combined use with Gumimax (Average 2019-2021)									
1	Shams	Control	45,1	5807607	1550	6990500	1182893	262,3	20,4
2		Ento PIK(Etalon)10%+Gumimax	56,7	6277607	1550	8788500	2510893	442,8	40,

3	Khim Askial 10% KE+Gumimax	66,6	6397607	1550	10323000	3925393	589,4	61,4
4	Demetra em.k + Gumimax	69,4	6517607	1550	10757000	4239393	610,9	65
5	Katsumii 24 ES+Gumimax	68,9	6477607	1550	10679500	4201893	609,9	64,9
6	Khimstar 75% V.D.G+Gumimax	56,4	6027607	1550	8742000	2714393	481,3	45
7	Adyu+Bomba V.D.G+Gumimax	71,5	6587607	1550	11082500	4494893	628,7	68,2

The gross income of 6,990,500 soums/ha was obtained in the variants that used low-toxic herbicides together with Gumimax compared to the control variant.

The net income from the sale of grain was 1182892.8 soums in the control option, compared to the control option, the highest net income in the options where herbicide and Gumimax were used was Adyu+Bomba v.d.g 0.2 l/ha; 4494892.8 soums/ha at the rate of 30 g/ha, Demetra em.k herbicide is 4239392.8 soums/ha at the rate of 0.5 l/ha, Katsumii 24 es is 4201892.8 soums at the rate of 0.3 l/ha , the lowest indicator was observed in the standard and Khimstar 75% V.D.G+Gumimax option.

The level of profitability increased by 40.0% compared to the benchmark option. The highest profitability was 68.2% when Adyu 0.2 l/ha+Bomba v.d.g 30 g/ha+Gumimax 0.5 l/ha was used in the norm, Katsumii 24 es 0.3 l/ha+Gumimax was used in the norm 64.9% in the variant, and 65.0% in the variant using Demetra em.k+Gumimax at the rate of 0.5 l/ha.

So, Adyu+Bomba v.d.g 0.2 l/ha against the main weeds found in irrigated autumn grain; Combined application of Gumimax 0.5 l/ha at the rate of 30 g/ha provides effective reduction of weeds and high grain yield. Also, using Demetra em.k 0.5 l/ha, and Katsumii 24 es 0.3 l/ha together with Gumimax reduces the number of one-year grain-like and one-year dicotyledonous weeds and stops them from growing, resulting in a higher and better grain yield and allows for economic efficiency (Table 1).

If herbicides are used in excess of the prescribed rate, they have a negative effect on cultivated plants. Do not use the same herbicide on the same field for more than two years. Otherwise, poison-resistant generations of weeds will be formed, as a result, the intended effect will not be achieved.

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